

IAU Symposium #385

“Astronomy and Satellite Constellations: Pathways Forward”

La Palma, Canary Islands, Spain, 2–6 October 2023

Connie Walker (NSF’s NOIRLab)

Regarding astronomy and satellite constellations, are you interested in

- the latest news on the impact of satellite constellations on astronomy?
- meeting the people at the forefront of this work?
- sharing your knowledge and efforts in this area through networking or contributed talks?
- helping to shape the next steps in protecting our dark and quiet skies from satellite constellation interference?

Then please join us online or in-person for the [IAU Symposium on Astronomy and Satellite Constellations: Pathways Forward](#) on the island of La Palma in the Canary Islands of Spain from 02 to 06 October 2023.

The proliferation of satellites launched into orbit around the Earth has improved our ability to instantly communicate globally; however, there are concerns about the impact these technologies have on astronomical observations and the preservation of dark and quiet skies. The rapid growth in light pollution, which is exacerbated by the new satellites, affects the entirety of society. Many people have never seen a truly dark night sky, and over a third of humanity cannot see the

Milky Way. These new satellites are encroaching on the few remaining dark-sky reserves and radio-quiet zones.

To address these challenges, IAU Symposium 385 is being held with the support of the International Astronomical Union (IAU)’s newest specialist center, the Center for the Protection of the Dark and Quiet Sky from Satellite Constellation Interference (CPS), and co-hosted by NSF’s NOIRLab and the Square Kilometer Array Observatory (SKAO). The symposium’s local organizer is the Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias. Information on the members of the local and scientific organizing committees is available on the [symposium organizers web page](#).

The symposium is planned as a dedicated space where astronomers, industry, space lawyers, and other interested stakeholders can share the current status of their work with respect to large satellite constellations and the impact on astronomy and the night sky. Through presentations, panel discussions, and networking, the current status of studies, observations, and mitigations will be explored, and gaps will be addressed to help define further the pathways forward.

Visit the [symposium website](#) for more information, including details on [registration and fees payment](#).

IAUS385 SYMPOSIUM

IN PERSON AND ONLINE MEETING

2-6 October 2023

Santa Cruz de La Palma, Canary Islands, SPAIN

Astronomy & Satellite Constellations: Pathways Forward

<https://research.iac.es/congreso/iaus385>

©Joshua Rozells

